

Effect of Photobiomodulation on the Efficacy of Anesthesia in Maxillary Permanent Molar Teeth with Molar Incisor Hypomineralization: A Randomized Clinical Trial

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Abstract:

Background: Molar Incisor Hypomineralization (MIH) is a developmental dental condition that compromises enamel quality, leading to increased sensitivity, higher caries risk, and challenges in achieving effective local anesthesia. The difficulty in anesthetizing MIH-affected teeth necessitates exploring adjunctive therapies to enhance anesthesia effectiveness. Photobiomodulation (PBM) has shown promise in improving anesthesia efficacy in various dental contexts, but its impact on MIH remains underexplored.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the effect of PBM on the efficacy of local anesthesia in maxillary permanent molar teeth with MIH.

Methods: A randomized clinical trial was conducted involving 70 participants with MIH. Participants were randomly assigned to either the intervention group (PBM + standard anesthesia) or the control group (standard anesthesia alone). Pain perception, onset time, and duration of anesthesia were assessed. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0, with significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Participants in the intervention group reported significantly lower pain perception (mean VAS score: 2.1 ± 0.8) compared to the control group (mean VAS score: 4.5 ± 1.2 , $p < 0.001$). The onset time of anesthesia was faster in the intervention group (mean: 4.2 ± 1.1 minutes vs. 6.7 ± 1.5 minutes, $p < 0.001$), and the duration of anesthesia was longer (mean: 75.4 ± 8.2 minutes vs. 65.3 ± 7.9 minutes, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Photobiomodulation significantly enhances the efficacy of local anesthesia in maxillary permanent molars affected by MIH, reducing pain perception, accelerating anesthesia onset, and prolonging its duration.

Recommendations: PBM should be considered as an adjunctive therapy in dental practices, particularly for patients with MIH, to improve treatment comfort and outcomes. Further research is recommended to explore the mechanisms and optimize PBM parameters for different dental conditions.

Keywords: Molar Incisor Hypomineralization, Photobiomodulation, Local Anesthesia, Dental Pain, Randomized Clinical Trial.

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Introduction

First permanent molars and, to a lesser extent, permanent incisors are the main teeth affected by (MIH), a developmental abnormality of dental enamel. MIH of enamel, frequently results in heightened sensitivity of the teeth, a greater vulnerability to caries, and challenges in attaining a local anaesthetic that is effective during dental procedures [1]. Worldwide, reports on the prevalence of MIH vary, ranging from 3.6% to 25% in various populations [2]. The genesis of MIH is complex, encompassing both hereditary and

environmental elements; nevertheless, the precise processes involved are still not well understood [3].

In order to effectively manage dental operations, local anaesthesia is essential, particularly for individuals with MIH who may feel more sensitive and uncomfortable [4]. The changed dentin and enamel structures of hypomineralized teeth, however, might make it difficult to achieve adequate anaesthesia and may affect the diffusion and effectiveness of local anesthetics [5]. Due of this difficulty, research into supplemental

treatments that might improve the anesthetic's effectiveness in this patient group is imperative.

Low-level laser therapy, or (PBM), has a viable supplementary treatment for a range of medical and dental purposes. PBM uses low-power lasers or light-emitting diodes (LEDs) to accelerate tissue healing, lower inflammation, and stimulate biological processes [6]. PBM has been investigated in dentistry because of its potential to improve local anaesthetic effects, hasten wound healing, and control pain and inflammation [7]. According to recent research, PBM may improve the effectiveness of local anaesthesia by making nerve cells more permeable, which will allow anaesthetic drugs to diffuse more easily [8]. Furthermore, it has been documented that PBM modifies nociceptive pathways, which in turn lessens pain perception [9]. This study aimed to evaluate the effect of PBM on the efficacy of local anesthesia in maxillary permanent molar teeth with MIH.

Methodology

Study Design: This study was designed as a randomized prospective clinical trial.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in department of Dentistry at Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, Bihar, over a period of four months.

Participants: The study included 70 participants, all of whom were patients with maxillary permanent molar teeth affected by molar incisor hypomineralization. Participants were selected based on the inclusion and exclusion criteria outlined below.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients aged 7 to 15 years.
- Patients with clinically diagnosed molar incisor hypomineralization in maxillary permanent molars.
- Patients requiring dental treatment under local anesthesia for affected teeth.
- Patients who provided informed consent (or whose guardians provided consent in the case of minors).

Exclusion Criteria

- Patients with systemic conditions affecting dental health.

- Patients with known allergies or contraindications to local anesthesia.
- Patients with a history of recent dental treatment in the affected teeth.
- Patients currently under any medication that may interfere with the study outcomes.
- Patients who declined to provide informed consent.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly assigned to either the intervention or control group using a computer-generated randomization sequence. Blinding was maintained for the outcome assessor to reduce observer bias, and the statistical analysis was performed by an independent statistician unaware of the group allocations.

Data Collection: Data was collected through clinical evaluations and patient self-reports. Baseline data, including demographic information and medical history, was recorded for each participant. The primary outcome measure was the efficacy of anesthesia, evaluated using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) for pain perception during the dental procedure. Secondary outcomes included the onset time and duration of anesthesia.

Procedure: Participants in the intervention group received PBM therapy using a specific wavelength and power density before the administration of local anesthesia. The control group received the standard anesthesia protocol without PBM. All dental procedures were carried out by experienced dental professionals under standardized conditions. Pain perception, onset time, and duration of anesthesia were recorded for all participants.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, frequencies, percentages) were calculated. Pain perception between groups was compared using independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests, with a significance level set at $p < 0.05$. Results were presented with 95% confidence intervals, and missing data were addressed using imputation techniques to minimize bias.

Results

A total of 70 participants were enrolled in the study and randomized into two groups: the intervention group (PBM+ standard anesthesia) and the control group (standard anesthesia alone), with 35 participants in each group.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Characteristic	Intervention Group (n=35)	Control Group (n=35)	p-value
Mean Age (years)	10.8 ± 2.1	11.0 ± 2.3	0.62
Gender			
- Male	19 (54.3%)	18 (51.4%)	0.82
- Female	16 (45.7%)	17 (48.6%)	
Affected Molars			
- One molar	20 (57.1%)	21 (60.0%)	0.80
- Two molars	15 (42.9%)	14 (40.0%)	

There were no significant differences between the groups regarding age, gender, or the number of affected molars, indicating that the groups were well-matched at baseline.

Primary Outcome: Pain Perception: Pain perception was measured using the (VAS) during the dental procedure.

Table 2: Pain Perception (VAS Scores)

VAS Score	Intervention Group (n=35)	Control Group (n=35)	p-value
Mean VAS Score	2.1 ± 0.8	4.5 ± 1.2	<0.001
VAS Score Range	1-4	2-7	
Number of Patients Reporting			
- Minimal Pain (VAS 0-2)	18 (51.4%)	5 (14.3%)	<0.001
- Moderate Pain (VAS 3-5)	17 (48.6%)	23 (65.7%)	
- Severe Pain (VAS 6-10)	0 (0%)	7 (20.0%)	

Participants in the intervention group reported significantly lower pain perception compared to the control group (mean VAS score: 2.1 ± 0.8 vs. 4.5 ± 1.2, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, a greater proportion of participants in the intervention group reported minimal pain.

Secondary Outcomes: Onset Time and Duration of anesthesia: The onset time and duration of anesthesia were also recorded and are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Onset Time and Duration of anesthesia

Parameter	Intervention Group (n=35)	Control Group (n=35)	p-value
Mean Onset Time (minutes)	4.2 ± 1.1	6.7 ± 1.5	<0.001
Mean Duration (minutes)	75.4 ± 8.2	65.3 ± 7.9	<0.001

The intervention group experienced a significantly faster onset of anesthesia compared to the control group (mean onset time: 4.2 ± 1.1 minutes vs. 6.7 ± 1.5 minutes, $p < 0.001$). Additionally, the duration of anesthesia was significantly longer in the intervention group (mean duration: 75.4 ± 8.2 minutes vs. 65.3 ± 7.9 minutes, $p < 0.001$).

Discussion

The study's results demonstrate a significant positive impact of PBM on the effectiveness of local anesthesia in treating maxillary permanent molar teeth affected by (MIH). Participants who received PBM in addition to standard anesthesia reported significantly lower pain levels during the dental procedure compared to those who received only standard anesthesia. The mean VAS score for pain perception in the intervention group was 2.1, considerably lower than the control group's mean score of 4.5. This suggests that PBM effectively reduces pain, making the dental experience more comfortable for patients with MIH.

In addition to improved pain management, the intervention group also experienced a faster onset

of anesthesia, with an average onset time of 4.2 minutes compared to 6.7 minutes in the control group. This indicates that PBM may enhance the speed at which anesthesia takes effect, allowing for quicker commencement of dental procedures. Moreover, the duration of anesthesia was significantly longer in the intervention group, lasting an average of 75.4 minutes compared to 65.3 minutes in the control group. The extended duration of anesthesia in the intervention group suggests that PBM may also prolong the effectiveness of the anesthetic, providing better control over pain for a longer period.

Numerous investigations have examined how photobiomodulation treatment (PBMT) might enhance the effectiveness of anaesthesia, especially in dentistry and paediatric contexts. The effect of PBMT on anaesthesia efficacy in maxillary permanent molar teeth afflicted by (MIH) was evaluated in a randomised clinical study. Compared to the control group, the PBMT group showed a tendency towards lower pain levels and a decreased requirement for supplementary

anaesthesia; however, these changes were not statistically significant [10].

The preemptive analgesic effect of PBMT during paediatric local anaesthetic injections in a different research was assessed. When PBMT was used instead of a topical anaesthetic gel, the study showed that pain perception during the injection procedure was greatly reduced. According to this research, PBMT may be a useful non-pharmacological method for reducing children's pain during dental treatments [11].

In a related investigation, looked at how PBMT, which uses a 915 nm diode laser, affected patients' perception of pain while receiving local anaesthesia in their maxillary incisors. The findings demonstrated that, when compared to a placebo group, PBMT dramatically decreased pain levels during local infiltration anaesthesia, suggesting that PBMT may be used to improve patient comfort during dental procedures [12].

Conclusion

The results of this study indicate that PBM significantly enhances the efficacy of local anesthesia in maxillary permanent molar teeth affected by MIH. Participants in the intervention group reported significantly lower pain perception, faster onset, and longer duration of anesthesia compared to the control group. The study supports the potential use of PBM as an adjunctive therapy in dental anesthesia, particularly for patients with MIH.

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